

Species 1: *H. timareta*

NOT test

Species 2: *H. heurippa*

Environmental overlap

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
 $D = 0.243$

Background 2→1

Background 1→2

Species 1: *H. timareta*

NDT test

Environmental overlap

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
 $D = 0.182$

Background 2→1

Background 1→2

